

Training Of Mathematic Students In Scientific Research Methods Based On The Solution Of A Complex Of Geometric Problems

M.M.Esonov

associate professor Kokand State Pedagogical Institute (Uzbekistan) esonovm@mail.ru

Abstract: *The article is devoted to the problem of visualization of abstract knowledge. In the Soviet secondary school, there was always an attitude toward the development of thinking, and its forms were different. Geometry, as the main bearer of the ideas of logic and figurative representation of abstract mathematical objects, had its rightful place in the system of mathematical education. Now, due to the transformations of the end of the last century in the USSR and the search for optimal development in the former Soviet republics, a natural experiment has taken place and the harmfulness of hasty decisions made by some ministries of education has become obvious. The article explicitly declares the need to restore geometry to its "rights" both in the school course and in pedagogical institutes.*

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INTRODUCTION.

Issues of history and some aspects of mathematical education in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The modern period of development of our civilization is characterized by a continuous increase in exchange and an increase in density, as well as the speed of information flows. This becomes an objective reason for the increase in the volume of communications, provided that knowledge does not change, and sometimes increases per unit time, as well as the need for its recording (by the teacher), processing (perception by the student) and preservation in the educational process of high school, enriching the personal environment.

Globalization is associated with many changes in the structure of education in Uzbekistan, which naturally forced us to study the experience of educational development in other countries - China, Russia, India, Japan, Singapore, and its use allows us to adjust the paths and directions of development in education systems.

Mathematical education, as history shows, is always at the forefront of the development of educational systems. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, mathematical education is also undergoing a change, primarily at the request of the state, since the development of rich mineral resources, industry, and energy require highly qualified specialists who are proficient in modern methods of studying natural and social phenomena.

By Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 13, 1998 No. 203, schooling became a nine-year education and a three-year specialized education, that is, 9 + 3. In accordance with the national education program, starting this year, Uzbek schoolchildren, after nine years of study in secondary school, continued their studies for another three years in academic lyceums and vocational

colleges. This approach, as it was believed at that time, made it possible to train the younger generation at the level of world standards, to train specialists taking into account the economic and demographic conditions of each local labor market.

It took the Republic of Uzbekistan 20 years of experimentation in the educational system for the authorities of this leading Central Asian country to think about returning 11 years of schooling, which was abolished in 1997.

Only the head of state could take the initiative to return everything "to normal," as is customary in the East. The President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, speaking at one of the meetings, explained to his subordinates what is the advantage of an 11-year education, that "in high school, children develop as individuals and unite into a team. It is during this period that they cannot be separated from their usual environment. This can negatively affect the psychology of young people, and ultimately, the level of education and upbringing. Therefore, it is necessary to ensure the continuity of the educational process and improve educational programs," summed up the President of Uzbekistan.

According to experts, the transition to 9-year education in Uzbekistan, which for many years was considered one of the achievements of its independence, did not justify itself.

Our joint history of development in the Russian state, in the Soviet Union, historical roots, the rich scientific heritage of our people, Eastern wisdom give hope for the organization of a new mathematical education that corresponds to the historical moment. Mention should be made of the Uzbek schools of functional analysis and probability theory, which occupy a worthy place in the outstanding Soviet mathematical school, consisting of Moscow, St. Petersburg, Kyiv and Novosibirsk, etc. Students of the Uzbek mathematical school are now working fruitfully in the republic and in other countries, supporting its name .

The main task of mathematical education is to develop the student's thinking and develop practical skills.

There are many ways of learning, among them there are old, well-tested ones, associated primarily with culture, but there are both undeservedly forgotten and new ones that have arisen in the modern socio-technical system of states.

We consider geometry to be undeservedly forgotten and relegated to the margins of modern curricula at pedagogical universities, as well as its important component - descriptive geometry. Geometry is the most important mathematical section. It has enormous developmental potential, which is poorly used by modern schools. Let us remember that even in antiquity mathematicians were called geometers, and in medieval Rus' engineers were called philosophers.

As psychologists recognize, one of the ways to consolidate and create conditions for intensifying the use of educational information is its visualization and reference to the student's speech activity. These qualities are effectively developed in schoolchildren in geometry lessons [1; 2]. In geometry lessons, the student not only thinks, reasons, understands, saves, applies in practice, but also conveys the imaginary, through a drawing, i.e., based on a graphical representation, a condition given in abstract form, solves some geometric problem visually. In this educational process, the habit of thinking specifically is developed, using various methods for reasoning, including visualization, ordering, logical generalizations, and logical-semantic construction. As our experience and research by psychologists shows, visualization is the first step to interpreting knowledge, to developing the thought process and to putting it into verbal forms in your native language.

3. Mastering the methods of descriptive geometry contributes to the effective development of spatial concepts in future mathematics teachers.

With the help of modern computer application packages, the learning process can be even more fruitful. However, we believe that modern auxiliary technology is certainly useful, but in the first stages of teaching the subject, the old natural tools of geometers are needed: a ruler, a compass and a pencil. Skills are required to convert three-dimensional space into two-dimensional space, real objects into imaginary ones on a plane, constructing and cutting objects.

4. Computer packages of application programs should help, but not replace traditional methods of teaching geometric sections of mathematics: elementary geometry, descriptive geometry and computer geometry.

In geometry lessons, skills in projection, determination of sections, and various symmetries are developed. Our methodology gives preference to the study of the topic "Construction Problems", in which the student simultaneously adapts the condition of the problem to the tools, imagines and applies a thought experiment in educational activities, and checks in practice the results of his imaginary reflections in exercises. And the imaginary "comes to life" in the drawing. The same skills are developed in drawing lessons, but speech activity is poorly used here [2;3]. Students conduct an analysis

of an imaginary object, a process of speculative operation arises, then visualization, but there is no strict justification for the construction of the result obtained. There is a representation of form, but no verbal representation of meaning. Therefore, the task arises - training future teachers in ways to extract, organize and adapt information in the learning process, students in a changing information environment. This means that the methodological "arsenal" of a mathematics student-teacher must include techniques and methods for working with information flows of increasing complexity and density, but at the same time, information tools remain such as long as the person who owns them has comprehended the essence of the subject.

The approximate program includes questions of construction using a compass and ruler, for the study of which 16 hours are allotted in the 3rd semester, and 24 hours in the 4th semester for constructing sections of polyhedra.

In the vast majority of tasks related to constructions on images, it is necessary to construct sections of given spatial figures. The methods for defining sections are very different, and there is no universal method for constructing them. The most effective in teaching practice in secondary school are the following three methods: 1) the trace method; 2) internal design method; 3) combined method. Let's consider one of these methods.

Trace method. In the general case, the section plane has a common straight line with the plane of each face of the polyhedron. The straight line along which the cutting plane intersects the plane of any face of the polyhedron is called the trace of the cutting plane. It is clear that a cutting plane has as many traces as the number of face planes it intersects. In practice, most often they find the trace of the cutting plane that lies in the plane of the lower base of the polyhedron. To develop spatial representation, it is necessary to solve problems of constructing sections, in which it is more expedient to find the trace of the cutting plane in the plane of some face different from the plane of the lower base of the polyhedron.

When constructing sections, the trace of the cutting plane plays a special role. So, let the lateral edges of a certain polyhedron be parallel and the line XY be the trace of the plane intersecting this polyhedron. Then if points K and L lie in the cutting plane, and points K_1 and L_1 are their projections onto the plane of the face in which the trace XY lies (and, naturally, the lines KK_1 and LL_1 are parallel to the side edge of the polyhedron), then the point of intersection of the lines KL and K_1L_1 lies on the XY trace.

This statement underlies the construction of sections of polyhedra using the trace method. To find a specific trace of a cutting plane, it is necessary, in addition to indicating the points that define the cutting plane, to also indicate (set or find) parallel projections of these points onto the plane of the face in which the trace is sought. So, if you need to construct a trace of a secant plane on the plane of the lower base of a parallelepiped, then, in addition to points lying directly in the secant plane, it is also necessary to indicate parallel projections

of these points onto the plane of the lower base (in the direction parallel to the side edge of the parallelepiped).

Rice. 1. Constructing a section using the trace method

Example 1. Points P, Q and R are taken on the edges of the parallelepiped ABCDA1B1C1D1 as follows: point P lies on edge CC1, point Q on edge DD1, point R on edge A1B1 (Fig. 1). Let's construct the trace of the cutting plane on the ABC plane.

Solution. Let's construct points P1, Q1 and R1 - projections of points P, Q and R onto the ABC plane. Since, by condition, point P lies on edge CC1, then, projecting it in a direction parallel to the side edge of the parallelepiped, we obtain point P1, coinciding with point C. Similarly, we obtain point Q1, which coincides with point D. Let us then draw in the plane AA1B1 through the point R straight line $\gamma \parallel AA1$ and find point R1 - the point of intersection of straight lines γ and AB.

Now that the projections of the points P, Q and R have been found, let's construct the points lying on the desired trace. Since $PP1 \parallel AA1$ and $RR1 \parallel AA1$, then $PP1 \parallel RR1$, i.e. straight lines PR and P1R1 lie in the same plane (it is determined by straight lines PP1 and RR1). Let's find point X - the point of intersection of these lines. It is clear that since point X lies on the straight line PR, then it lies in the cutting plane, and since it lies on the straight line P1R1, then it lies in the ABC plane - the plane of the lower base. So, point X belongs to both the cutting plane and the base plane, i.e., it belongs to the desired trace.

Similarly, we find point Y - the point of intersection of lines PQ and P1Q1. Point Y, like point X, belongs to the desired trace. Thus, the desired trace is the XY line.

We found the trace of the cutting plane as the XY line. If, for example, instead of point Y we find point Z (the intersection point of the lines RQ and R1Q1), then since point X and point Z both belong to both the cutting plane and the plane of the base, then straight line XZ will also be a trace of the cutting plane PQR. The question arises, are the lines XY and XZ the same?

Clearly, since the points P, Q and R belong to the same plane, and the points P1, Q1 and R1 also belong to the same plane, and the points X, Y and Z belong to each of these planes,

then the points X, Y and Z lie on the intersection line these planes. In other words, the trace of the cutting plane is uniquely determined by its two points. (Teacher, in this regard, we can recall a special case of Desargues' theorem, from which it follows that since the lines PP1, QQ1 and RR1 are parallel to each other, then the indicated points X, Y and Z belong to the same line.)

6. Every mathematics teacher must adhere to the student-mathematics-pedagogy-student scheme (home studies - Human student).

What does this mean, he must take into account the characteristics of the student, their capabilities, the specific features of the subject, the psychological, pedagogical and age characteristics of the student, and also instill in the future teacher the skill of being students for the rest of his life. Abilities such as visual memory, visualization skills, mnemonic techniques, and stereographic thinking are developed most of all in geometry lessons. Geometric problems involving the construction of sections of spatial figures with a plane are not such a quickly solvable problem. The solution of such geometric problems for the student, if he studies at home, develops new ways of visualization. For a solid assimilation of knowledge on the construction and development of stereographic thinking skills, it would be advisable if hours were devoted to the topic "Construction", a separate semester and a course of projective geometry was taught not four hours of lectures and the same number of hours of practical training. This course, combined with descriptive geometry, as a course in the study of scientific methods of visualization, information processing and programming languages, would be rich in techniques for developing the necessary skills that would become habits of mathematics educators. Obviously, in any field of mathematics it would be useful to translate the imaginary into a visual drawing or diagram.

A modern biologist, engineer or many other specialists use an auxiliary computer mechanism in the role of office equipment to accurately coordinate a situation and comprehend it, but no one has canceled critical thinking. When solving a geometric problem, a specialist translates the imaginary into a visual image, a meaningful idea of the object.

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